

A Preliminary Note on a New Method of Synthesising Benzopyrylium Compounds.

BY M. N. GOSWAMI AND AMIYA KUMAR CHAKRAVARTI.

While studying some reactions of coumarin, the authors had come across a remarkable reaction between it and resorcin in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. A mixture of coumarin (8 g.), resorcin (6 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 c. c.) was heated with an air condenser on the water-bath until the red solution so formed became thick. On cooling and being treated with ice-cold dry ether (in which both coumarin and resorcin are freely soluble) an orange-red compound was precipitated. On washing with dry ether it was obtained as brilliant scales from alcohol, m. p. 185° (decomp.). It is insoluble in ether, carbon disulphide and other common organic solvents except alcohol. It is appreciably soluble in water. It dissolves in alkali to a reddish brown solution, the colour of which is discharged by acid. It contains chlorine and is highly hygroscopic. The compound was kept for about six months in a vacuum desiccator and on analysis it was found to contain C, 54.5; H, 5.72;* whilst $C_{15}H_{11}O_3Cl, 3H_2O$ requires C, 51.79; H, 5.14 per cent. The behaviour of the compound is similar to that of benzopyrylium salt and it was thought that the compound had the following structure (I) and it had been formed in the following way:

The extreme hygroscopic nature of the compound causes great difficulty in its analysis and this is responsible for the high value of hydrogen. This difficulty has been experienced with pyrylium compounds by many other workers.

If this representation is correct then the compound is 2',4'-dihydroxy-2-phenylbenzopyrylium chloride. On reference to the literature it was found that this compound had not yet been synthesised.

An attempt was then made to synthesise the compound after the method of Robinson and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1951) from salicylaldehyde and resacetophenone. It was found that although the intermediate styryl compound was easily obtained, the final stage to close up the ring always led to the formation of tarry matter. The attempt in this direction having proved abortive, the dimethoxy derivative of the original compound was prepared by taking dimethoxyresorcin, coumarin and phosphorus oxychloride. It gave a ferrichloride as orange-red needle shaped crystals, m. p. 175° (A). (Found: Cl, 30.58; Fe, 11.85. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3$, $FeCl_4$ requires Cl, 30.54; Fe, 12.04 per cent.).

This dimethoxy derivative was, however, successfully prepared by the ordinary synthetic method, *via* salicylaldehyde and dimethoxyresacetophenone. It was obtained (B) as orange-red needle shaped crystals, m. p. 175°. (Found: Cl, 30.52; Fe, 12.06. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3$, $FeCl_4$ requires Cl, 30.54; Fe, 12.04 per cent.). Mixed melting point of (A) and (B) was also found to be 175°. The compound (A) is therefore identical with compound (B) both of which have the following structure as proved by synthesis.

This compound, too, has not been synthesised as yet.

Almost all other phenols and phenolic ethers have been found to condense similarly with coumarin and substituted coumarins in presence of phosphorus oxychloride to give benzopyrylium compounds and they will be published in a future communication. The method gives a new and an easy way to prepare various types of benzopyrylium salts and undoubtedly opens a vast field of possibilities which the authors desire to explore.